

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN SUBSYSTEMS OF STUDENT LEARNING ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

The article argues the relevance of the topic, the expediency of expressing the concept of "student's independent work" as a "subsystem of student learning activities", and defines independent work through the concept of "subsystem". It is emphasized that the subsystem of activity in the learning process, which is characterized by the fact that the student performs the task of the teacher without direct assistance, corresponding to the degree of independence, is called his independent work.

The article provides a classification of requirements for independent work and types of independent work based on the generalization of materials obtained in the research process.

It is noted that due to the view of the concept of "independent work" as a subsystem, the existing "gaps" in the theory of the concept and its applications are largely eliminated.

Consideration of the concept of "independent work" as a subsystem creates an environment for the elimination of errors in the activities of teachers in terms of their selection, systematization and application.

Keywords: Independent work, activity, subsystem, problem situation, provocative, constructive

Relevance of the research topic. The interpretation of the concept of independent work as one of the subsystems of students' learning activities not only reduces the errors in pedagogical considerations related to the nature of independent work, but also provides a scientific basis for defining its nomenclature and classification. Therefore, we claim the relevance of this research topic, which is based on a "system-structural" approach.

Interpretation of research materials. There are four directions in the activity of the personality: cognitive activity with self and the values of the world around it, the activity of preserving the originality of human achievements, the activity of transforming the world and oneself from a biological being to a social being according to the degree of ascension, activity of entering into a relationship normalized with human values.

Professor L.B. Itelson believes that a relatively finished element of activity in one direction or another aimed at solving a simple current problem is called work. [6;169]. In our opinion, from the point of view of approaching the activity of the individual as a system, it would be more expedient to use the term "subsystem" instead of the term "relatively finished element".

Work, which is a subsystem of the system of activity of the individual, can be performed by the subject in independent or non-independent ways. There is a dialectical connection between activity and work, which is its subsystem. This applies to learning activities and their subsystems. In the process of learning, the student is able to perform a current task freely, both with the intervention of the teacher and without direct assistance, mentally and practically. The second case retains its essence in the concept of independent work.

The discovery of the concept and essence of the concept of "independent work" is closely linked with the concept of "independence of thought", which is the psychological basis of students' cognitive activity and activity. Understanding the essence of the independence of thinking, in addition to allowing to understand the essence of independent work, allows us to determine the degree of independence of students in different age groups, without which it is impossible to organize independent work of students in practice.

In order to organize the independent work of students in the learning process, it is necessary to properly understand the scientific and psychological nature of the independence of thinking.

In addition to forming the psychological basis of students' independent work, the independence of thinking is a very broad feature of the mind in practice, and it reflects a number of other features of the mind, including criticism. Without the participation of the critical nature of the mind, there can be no independent activity of thinking, no independent cognitive process, no independent work of students. The critical property of the mind is necessary in the activity of independence in order for the individual to be able to evaluate himself, to consider and compare the results of his activity, to point out mistakes and shortcomings, and to make sure that the chosen path is correct. Otherwise, it is difficult to say that independence is a full-fledged feature of thinking.

However, there are those who do not agree with the idea of limiting the independence of thought only to criticism. For example, S.L. Rubinstein believes that not only the critique of the mind, but also a number of other psychological abilities are included in the scope of activity of the independence of thought. Among them, first of all, it is necessary to note the will, although psychologists consider "independence" to be an

important feature of the will, M.M. Mehdizadeh agrees that students' independent work, even in any variant, faces certain difficulties. They need to be eliminated. It is known that a student with weak willpower can not cope with the task. Thus, voluntary activity also in a sense becomes a component of independence of thought. [7;187]

According to M.A. Ismikhonov, the independence of thinking is mainly expressed in the fact that the student is mentally active, solves a certain cognitive problem on his own, is critical of his activities and is independent of thought. The student's independence in training is closely linked to his activity. [4;19]

Undoubtedly, the activity of the student is an important condition for his independence: independence is possible on the basis of a certain mental and practical activity of the student. Activity, in turn, requires a certain degree of independence from the student, and the more independence the student shows in learning, the more active he becomes. [4; 20] We can agree with the views of M.M. Mehdizade and M.A. Ismikhonov.

The methodological basis of the problem is the connection of the category of "freedom" in philosophy with training. In philosophy, the concept of "freedom" is rightly considered, on the one hand, as a link between freedom and necessity in the lives of large masses of people, in its general-historical plan, on the other hand, in the subjective-moral aspect, it is understood as an internal activity of an individual. M.G. Mislivchenko noted, in the first aspect the formula "freedom" is mostly related to politics, in the second aspect it is related to pedagogy and psychology. [9;128]

M.M. Mehdizadeh connected freedom with activity and wrote that the independence of the individual is formed in the process of active participation in public life, including training, ie in the process of active social activity. The development of an individual's independence, that is, his or her ability to make independent decisions, reflects the fact that he or she makes a practical decision, solves any task in the interests of the social group he or she belongs to, and is accountable to that group. [7; 193]. "It is through the independent solution of the tasks set by life that the responsibility of the individual develops as an organic function of his independence," - said A.I. Romanyuk is right and in this regard, M.M. Mehdizadeh shows that only one note can be added to all this: "The sense of responsibility of the individual in the conditions of his inner activity, in the conditions of his creative and managerial-executive activity, is essentially the main line of his independence." [7;193-194]

Although we do not have a serious objection to this, we need an addition that the concepts of "freedom", "independence" and "activism" should be considered in a dialectical relationship for all aspects. Thus, man accepts his freedom according to the degree to which he understands reality and is able to change it, the perception of reality and its change, the acquisition of relevant experience depends on the independence of the individual, the corresponding activity. At the same time, what is perceived, the experience of perception, the experience of changing reality, further enhances the

independence of the individual. Therefore, the concepts of "freedom", "independence", "activity" can belong to a system of categories that condition each other and reflect the level of social formation of the individual. There is no denying the importance of independent work to form the independence of the individual, to develop the activities of students, to strengthen their will, to overcome the difficulties encountered in the performance of tasks. In the learning process, the issues of "development of students' independence" and "organization and management of independent work" are based on each other, consistently and mutually perform the functions of cause and effect.

Based on our theoretical analysis and work experience, we consider it expedient to understand independent work as follows: the subsystem of activity characterized by the student's performance of the teacher's task without direct assistance in accordance with the degree of independence of the student in the learning process is called his independent work.

As can be seen, in the definition, the student's independent work is perceived as a subsystem of his learning activities. Thus, the dialectical relationship between the system and the subsystem, which is necessary for existence, is also emphasized between the learning activity and the student's independent work. That is, the student's independent work is based on the implementation of all didactic tasks set before the learning process. Therefore, the set goal must be understood by the student, that goal must become the object of meeting the cognitive needs of the student, and in order to fulfill the requirement of the set task, he must become the subject of the activity in which he is involved. In the process of independent work, the relationship between the managing, the managed and between them, the training material is changing and evolving. Unity, system, completeness, comprehensiveness, dependence, non-contradiction, regularity of non-independent work should be expected in independent work. Organizing and managing independent work is a purposeful mental activity of a teacher. Most importantly, it has algorithmic and heuristic features.

Independent work has relative independence as a subsystem. The means of its organization and regulation are questions, studies and issues.

While independent work in the learning process focuses on performing relatively independent functions, these functions stem from the overall objectives of the process. The place of independent work in the learning process is determined by the logic of the coordination and management of the components of this process.

The task for the organization of independent work is determined by the teacher for didactic purposes in accordance with the degree of independence of the student or pupils. The teacher performs organizational and regulatory functions with a task of a certain logical form. The main feature here is that the student's task is not interfered with in the process of execution, ensuring his conditions for independent activity. Independent work is a subsystem of the learning process and has the property of time constraints. It can be applied at

different stages of the learning process. Independent work accelerates the development of the student, expands the opportunities to perform specific teaching-cognitive and teaching-organizational functions, provides good management of the learning process.

There are a number of requirements for independent work of students, it is possible to divide these requirements into types and classify them. The psycho-didactic requirements for independent work include the following:

1. Independent work is designed in advance on the basis of the forthcoming didactic tasks.

The didactic task of each independent work is to keep two important directions:

1) The general purpose of the training process:

a) the assimilation of human experience in the course of its historical development;

b) experience in its protection;

c) To prepare man for the acquisition of the creative experience necessary for the civilization and freedom of the society to which he belongs;

d) the coexistence of people who are organically connected to the previous three purposes, and the acquisition of the qualities that make the world window open to them;

2) Transform the learning process into a well-managed process.

2. In order to organize and manage independent work, it is necessary to determine its place and the form of covering students.

Independent work can be applied to all stages of the training process:

a) substantiation of learning and actualization of past experience;

b) in the acquisition of knowledge;

c) application of knowledge in systematization;

d) in the evaluation of the process and results by the teacher and students themselves.

According to the form of coverage of students is defined as a) individual, b) double, c) group, d) frontal.

3. The duration of independent work, the coverage of past knowledge, the degree of difficulty of new knowledge, the suitability of students to their potential should be determined. Therefore, it should be clarified which of the different types included in the nomenclature of independent work will be applied.

4. The type of task should be selected in advance and the teacher should think carefully about the formula of the task. It is also important to seriously consider the capabilities of the school, the teacher's own training, the content of the training material, and the capabilities of the student (or students).

5. The terms and conditions of the assignment must be clear to the student. It is possible that as a logical continuation of the work, an assignment is formed for joint work with the student, and in this case there is no need for additional explanations and instructions. If so, the student must be given clear and concise instructions.

6. Consistency, systematization and development should be expected in the application of independent work. The importance of this work should be kept in

focus to prepare the student for independent and free education and life.

7. It is important to generalize, systematize, apply knowledge in changed situations and have new elements in students' independent work. The performance of independent work should guide the student to acquire more general knowledge, skills and habits, experience, while maintaining the requirement to be based on acquired knowledge, habits and skills, life experience, observations. Independent work should improve the student's interest and tendency to learn with its content, fun, logic. Independent work should stimulate the development of the student's ability to evaluate (correctly and fairly), which is considered one of the most important personal qualities.

8. The system of independent work must preserve the unity of mental and practical activity. In order to develop the algorithmic and heuristic aspects of the student's mental activity in independent work, to form his activity as a subject of management, the working conditions should be improved under the proper guidance of the teacher. The teacher's work should be constantly adjusted to the specific circumstances.

In the pedagogical literature, some of the classifications proposed as types of independent work are related to the functional aspect of independent work (work aimed at acquiring knowledge, forming and testing skills and habits), some to the level of students' independence in independent work (for example, reconstruction and creative work), some to the source of independent work. (work on books, information literature, problem solving and exercises, etc.), some to the degree of teacher's help (non-independent, semi-independent, fully independent work), and some to the form of organization of independent work (frontal, group, pair and individual work)) is indicated to be attributed. It is emphasized that independent types of work can have different content depending on the nature of individual subjects and the specific teaching situation.

The creative activity of the vast majority of teachers has had a strong impact on the improvement of the learning process and the collection of new pedagogical facts. The process of finding ways and means of students' cognitive activity has led to the renewal of pedagogical thought.

The results of the research of M.I. Mahmutov and others in the direction of combining problem-based learning with programmed training further enriched the nomenclature of independent work. [8;448] However, the problem has not yet been fully resolved. The theoretical and practical way of the dialectical unity of students' independent and non-independent work as subsystems of a single process has not been worked out in detail. In this case, the following points should be considered:

1) The course of the learning process in accordance with the didactic goals, the results of students' activities depend on the level of development of two important aspects of his mental activity - analytical (algorithmic) and heuristic types, their unity.

2) The direction and speed of the student's development depends on the types of activities they are involved in and their regulation. At the same time, the developmental characteristics of the student's personality are reflected in the activities to which they are involved.

Based on these two logical arguments, it can be said that the learning process should be based on the level of development of both types of mental activity of the student (algorithmic and heuristic), focusing on their further development (ensuring their unity). Independent work should include these aspects as a subsystem of learning activities.

The system of independent work and its nomenclature, which correspond to the logic of the learning process, include the optimal relationship of algorithmic and heuristic activities of students, which we consider practical and achieve effective results using in our work experience, are as follows:

1. A type of programmed or unprogrammed independent work aimed at making the goal of the learning process the object of meeting the needs of the student (or students).

We refer to this type of independent work as the following types: 1) Independent work on understanding the usefulness of the material for teaching, development, further activity; 2) Independent work that directs students to study the material with fun and attractive shades; 3) Independent work to create a problem situation.

2. The type of independent work (programmed or unprogrammed) used mainly in the ready transfer of knowledge and methods of action. This type: 1. We refer to the following types of independent work, mainly related to intellectual activity: 1) independent work that requires updating and recalling what has been learned in the past, 2) independent work that requires coaching, application of an important rule or law to similar situations, 3) explanatory and explanatory independent work, 4) independent work requiring justification, 5) independent work on algorithmization, 6) independent work on the application of knowledge in changed situations, 7) independent work on discussion, etc.

Types of independent work, mainly related to practical activities: 1) independent work of educational-practical nature: 2) independent work of social-practical nature.

3. Cognitive-search (heuristic) independent type of work used in problem-based learning.

We include the following types of independent work in this type: 1) Independent work on problem interpretation: elimination of contradictions, independent study of undisclosed (in the teacher's commentary) material, the student's ability to generalize; 2) Partially applied independent search operations; 3) Independent work managed through the application of the problem, question, work: provocative independent work, constructive, defining independent work, independent

work on experimental-search, independent work on logical-search, etc.

4. Type of creative independent work. The basic criterion for the acquisition of knowledge is its creative application [1; 336]. We distinguish the following types of this type of independent work: 1) artistic-figurative: 2) scientific-creative, 3) constructive-technical, 4) experimental-creative.

Scientific novelty of the research. The learning process was seen as a "broad system" in relation to the student activity it contained, in other words, the student's learning activity was perceived as a "small system" in relation to the system it contained. Continuing this logical approach, it was concluded that "students' independent work" is a subsystem of their learning activities. Thus, a new version of the theoretical and technological development of the inclusion of independent work in the learning process, which is a complete system, has been identified. This is a pedagogical, theoretical and technological innovation, with an approach based on philosophy and logic.

Theoretical significance of the research. Due to the view of the concept of "independent work" as a subsystem, the "gaps" in the theory of the concept and its applications are largely eliminated.

Practical significance of the research. Consideration of the concept of "independent work" as a subsystem creates an environment for the elimination of errors in the activities of teachers in terms of their selection, systematization and application.

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